

Supplementary Materials for "Multitarget Respiration Rate and DOA Estimation Using Sparse SIMO IR-UWB Radar Based On Fourth Order Cumulant"

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This document contains online supplementary materials complementing the main article entitled: "**Multitarget Respiration Rate and DOA Estimation Using Sparse SIMO IR-UWB Radar Based On Fourth Order Cumulant**". It includes additional figures, detailed tables, and appendixes that could not be included in the printed version due to space limitations. For the main text, please refer to the published paper.

1 Supplementary Equations

$$\mathbf{C}_S(f_i) = \mathbb{E} \left\{ (\mathbf{S}(f_i) \otimes \mathbf{S}(f_i)^*) (\mathbf{S}(f_i) \otimes \mathbf{S}(f_i)^*)^H \right\} - \mathbb{E} \left\{ (\mathbf{S}(f_i) \otimes \mathbf{S}(f_i)^*) \right\} \mathbb{E} \left\{ (\mathbf{S}(f_i) \otimes \mathbf{S}(f_i)^*)^H \right\} \\ - \mathbb{E} \left\{ (\mathbf{S}(f_i) \mathbf{S}(f_i)^H) \right\} \otimes \mathbb{E} \left\{ (\mathbf{S}(f_i) \mathbf{S}(f_i)^H)^* \right\} \quad (\text{S1})$$

$$\text{Error}_d = \frac{1}{M_c K} \sum_{m=1}^{M_c} \sum_{k=1}^K \frac{|d_{0_k} - \hat{d}_{0_k}[m]|}{|d_{0_k}|} \times 100\% \quad (\text{S2})$$

$$\text{Error}_{f_r} = \frac{1}{M_c K} \sum_{m=1}^{M_c} \sum_{k=1}^K \frac{|f_{r_k} - \hat{f}_{r_k}[m]|}{|f_{r_k}|} \times 100\%$$

2 Supplementary Figures

Figure S. 1 Received signal model in SIMO radar.

Figure S. 2 Overall scheme of the proposed method.

Figure S. 3 Principal of SS technique.

Figure S. 4 Comparison of physical sparse geometries of $N=6$ antennas and their virtual 4-DCs with 8-antennas ULA: (a) MRA. (b) 4-DC of MRA. (c) nested array. (d) 4-DC of nested array. (e) coprime array. (f) 4-DC of coprime array. (g) ULA with $N=8$ antennas.

Figure S. 5 Pseudo-spectrum comparison: (a): MUSIC-ULA $N = 14$, (b): MUSIC-ULA $N = 11$, (c): MUSIC-ULA $N = 8$, (d): FOC-SS-MUSIC for MRA $N = 6$, (e) FOC-SS-MUSIC for nested array $N = 6$, (f): FOC-SS-MUSIC for coprime array $N = 6$.

Figure S. 6 Pseudo-spectrum comparison in underdetermined case: (a): MUSIC-ULA $N = 14$, (b): MUSIC-ULA $N = 11$, (c): MUSIC-ULA $N = 8$, (d): FOC-SS-MUSIC for MRA $N = 6$, (e): FOC-SS-MUSIC for nested array $N = 6$, (f): FOC-SS-MUSIC for coprime array $N = 6$.

Figure S. 7 Estimated distance and respiratory frequency of different human targets in underdetermined case. (a): $\theta_1 = -45^\circ$, (b): $\theta_2 = -10^\circ$, (c): $\theta_3 = 0^\circ$, (d): $\theta_4 = 5^\circ$, (e): $\theta_5 = 10^\circ$, (f): $\theta_6 = 26^\circ$, (g): $\theta_7 = 30^\circ$.

Figure S. 8 Illustrative setup of closely spaced human targets.

Figure S. 9 Pseudo-spectrum comparison in dense scenario: (a): MUSIC-ULA $N = 14$, (b): MUSIC-ULA $N = 11$, (c): MUSIC-ULA $N = 8$, (d): FOC-SS-MUSIC for MRA $N = 6$, (e): FOC-SS-MUSIC for nested array $N = 6$, (f): FOC-SS-MUSIC for coprime array $N = 6$.

Figure S. 10 Error analysis in Underdetermined scenario. (a): Frequency. (b): Range.

Figure S. 11 Error analysis in dense scenario. (a): Frequency. (b): Range.

3 Supplementary Tables

Table S1 Comparison of Radar-Based Vital Sign Monitoring Techniques.

Radar type/ Method	Antenna configuration	No. of detected subjects	$\Delta\theta_{min}(\text{°})^1$	Key Features / Limitations	Refs.
CW Radar	MIMO (4T-4R ²)	Up to 3	13°	Simple SISO hardware; acceptable angular resolution in MIMO; increased RF channel complexity in SIMO/MIMO.	[2]
FMCW Radar	MISO (4T-1R)	2	30°	High carrier frequency and wide bandwidth; limited subject detection; coarse angular resolution.	[3]
IR-UWB Radar	SIMO (1T-8R)	Up to 3	15°	High range resolution and penetration; effective for multiple targets; limited angular separation.	[4]
STC Digital Metasurface Radar	1T-1R(virtual array via harmonics)	4	13°	Virtual sensor nodes via harmonic waves; detection limited by harmonic order; focus on breathing separation rather than explicit DOA.	[19]
Proposed IR- UWB with Sparse Arrays and FOC-SS- MUSIC	SIMO (1T-6R)	Up to 7	5°	Spectral approximation ensures source decorrelation; sparse arrays enlarge aperture; FOC suppresses Gaussian noise; robust in coherent and underdetermined scenarios.	This work

4 Supplementary Appendixes

4.1 Appendix A

A1. Role of fourth order difference co-array

Consider a sparse linear array of N physical elements positioned as in (1), from which, a virtual array referred to as the fourth-order difference coarray (4-DC) is constructed, providing a larger number of virtual elements than the physical configuration.

$$S = \{p_1, p_2, \dots, p_N\} \cdot d \quad (1)$$

¹ $\Delta\theta_{min}$ means the minimum separable angle interval between two sources.

²T means Transmitter and R means Receiver.

The 4-DC is defined as follows [11]:

$$C_{4\text{-DC}} = \Phi_{4\text{-DC}} \cdot d \quad (2)$$

where the set of 4-DC lags are the distinct elements of the set $\Phi_{4\text{-DC}}$ defined as:

$$\Phi_{4\text{-DC}} = \{(p_{n_1} + p_{n_2}) - (p_{n_3} + p_{n_4}), 1 \leq n_1, n_2, n_3, n_4 \leq N\} \quad (3)$$

which can be reformulated as:

$$\Phi_{4\text{-DC}} = \sum_{i=1}^2 p_{n_i} - \sum_{i=3}^4 p_{n_i}, \quad 1 \leq n_i \leq N \quad (4)$$

Let the spectral representation of received signal and the Single Measurement Vector (SMV) of Fourth Order Cumulant (FOC) of received signals, described in (5) and (6), respectively:

$$R_n(f_l) = \sum_{k=1}^K e^{-j2\pi f_l (p_n - 1) \frac{d}{c} \sin(\theta_k)} S_k(f_l) + W_n(f_l) \quad (5)$$

$$\mathbf{c}_R(f_l) = \mathbf{B}(\theta_k, f_l) \mathbf{c}_s(f_l) \in \mathbb{C}^{N^4 \times 1} \quad (6)$$

To establish the link between the SMV model in (6) and the 4-DC representation, based on (5), the source signals $S_k(f_l)$ are assumed to be non-Gaussian, mutually independent, and statistically independent of $W_n(f_l)$. By exploiting the additivity property of cumulants for independent components, and noting that the FOC of AWGN is zero, the resulting N^4 FOC values can be expressed as [16]:

$$\sum_{k=1}^K e^{-j2\pi f_l \frac{d}{c} (\sum_{i=1}^2 p_{n_i} - \sum_{i=3}^4 p_{n_i}) \sin \theta_k} c_{s_k}(f_l) \quad (7)$$

where $1 \leq n_i \leq N$, $1 \leq i \leq 4$, and $c_{s_k}(f_l) = \text{cum}\{S_{k_1}(f_l), S_{k_2}(f_l), S_{k_3}^*(f_l), S_{k_4}^*(f_l)\}$. Thus, the 4-DC expressed in (4) naturally arises in the FOC values. As a result, the model in (7) can be interpreted as the signal received by the virtual 4-DC, where the source term corresponds to the FOC of the source associated with the physical array. It is important to highlight that NULAs can generate significantly more elements in their higher-order difference co-arrays compared to ULAs [16].

A2. Distance and respiratory rate estimation

After DOA estimation and based on the spectral representation of the received signal in the selected optimal bandwidth B , for each frequency bin $f_l \in [f_c - \frac{B}{2}, f_c + \frac{B}{2}]$, a steering vector $\mathbf{a}_{das}(\hat{\theta}_k, f_l)$ is evaluated as given below:

$$\mathbf{a}_{das}(\hat{\theta}_k, f_l) = [1, e^{-j2\pi f_l \tau_2}, \dots, e^{-j2\pi f_l \tau_N}] \quad (8)$$

where:

$$\tau_n = (p_n - 1) \frac{d}{c} \sin(\hat{\theta}_k), \quad n = 2, \dots, N \quad (9)$$

The weighting vector is then calculated as given:

$$\mathbf{w}_{\text{DAS}_k} = \frac{\mathbf{a}_{das}(\hat{\theta}_k, f_l)}{\sqrt{\mathbf{a}_{das}(\hat{\theta}_k, f_l)^H \mathbf{a}_{das}(\hat{\theta}_k, f_l)}} \quad (10)$$

Thus, the weighted sum matrix of the k -th human target, denoted as $\mathbf{R}_{\text{DAS}_k}(f_l)$, can be defined as follows:

$$\mathbf{R}_{\text{DAS}_k}(f_l) = \mathbf{w}_{\text{DAS}_k}^H \mathbf{R}(f_l) \quad (11)$$

At this stage, the target-to-radar distance is estimated after converting the beamformed matrix $\mathbf{R}_{\text{DAS}_k}(f_l)$ into the time domain using the ICZT, by computing the fourth-order moment as follows:

$$\mu_k(j) = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{m=1}^M (\mathbf{R}_{\text{DAS}_k}(m, j) - \bar{y}_k(j))^4 \quad (12)$$

where \bar{y}_k is the mean vector of $\mathbf{R}_{\text{DAS}_k}$ over the slow time described as:

$$\bar{y}_k(j) = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{m=1}^M \mathbf{R}_{\text{DAS}_k}(m, j) \quad (13)$$

The distance of the k -th target is then estimated using the following equation:

$$\hat{d}_{0k} = \frac{c j_{max_k}}{2F_f} \quad (14)$$

where j_{max_k} denotes the index of the maximum value in the fourth-order moment vector μ_k , and F_f is the fast-time sampling frequency.

At this point, the estimation of the respiratory frequency of the k -th target is simply based on calculating the FFT of the j_{max_k} -th column of the matrix $\mathbf{R}_{\text{DAS}_k}$, as shown in the following equation:

$$V_k(f) = \sum_{m=1}^M \mathbf{R}_{\text{DAS}_k}(m, j_{max_k}) e^{-\frac{j2\pi f m}{M}} \quad (15)$$

Thus, the respiratory frequency is obtained as:

$$\hat{f}_{rk} = \frac{F_s}{M} \arg \max_f |V_k(f)| \quad (16)$$

where F_s and M correspond to the slow-time sampling frequency and the total number of acquired realizations, respectively.

A3. Effect of optimal bandwidth on target separability

The range resolution of the beamformed matrix, obtained after transformation into the time domain using the ICZT, is determined by the selected bandwidth B and can be expressed as:

$$\Delta R = \frac{c}{2B} \quad (17)$$

This relation highlights the inverse proportionality between the range resolution and the bandwidth B . A broader bandwidth enables higher temporal resolution, thereby allowing for finer discrimination between targets located at similar or close distances. Specifically, increasing B sharpens the main lobe of the time-domain response after ICZT, which reduces overlap between echoes from adjacent targets, thereby improving both target separability and estimation accuracy. This characteristic is particularly important in scenarios involving multiple human subjects in close proximity, where the ability to resolve individual reflections is critical for accurate localization and subsequent respiration frequency extraction.

In contrast, smaller values of B lead to degraded resolution, complicating the separation of targets with similar ranges and close angular positions. This degradation occurs because the corresponding impulse response in the time domain broadens, leading to significant overlap between the reflected signals of nearby targets. As a result, the beamformed output exhibits less pronounced peaks, making it difficult to distinguish individual reflections.